

Cross Cultural issues in Clinical Psychology
Africa International University (AIU), Department of Psychology
PhD Clinical Psychology, Nairobi, Kenya

COPING MECHANISMS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON MENTAL WELL-BEING AMONG ZULU AND MAASAI COMMUNITIES

A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Authors: Rupondo, P, Mwangi, A.

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KeyWords

Coping mechanisms, mental well-being, Zulu community, Maasai community, cross-cultural psychology, urban indigenous populations, cultural resilience, Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, mental health in Africa, comparative quantitative research.

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the coping mechanisms and their influence on the wellbeing of the Maasai and Zulu populations in Nairobi, Kenya, and Johannesburg, South Africa. Using stratified random sampling, 20 adults from each community participated in the study and completed structured questionnaires for the comparative quantitative research design. The cultural background, coping mechanisms, and mental wellbeing of the participants was evaluated. Data was analysed using statistical inferences to test correlation coefficient and variability and consistency of the findings. A negative association ($r = -0.7109$) approximately reached significance ($p = 0.0945$) between coping techniques and mental health in the Zulu population, according to the statistical data findings. Maasai community, on the other hand, showed a slightly negative connection that was not statistically significant ($r = -0.1126$, $p = 0.824$). Although more research with a larger sample size is necessary to confirm these findings, which indicate that coping techniques may have an impact on mental health, especially among the Zulu individuals.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of global mental health research, understanding the relationship amongst various indigenous cultural contexts and their coping mechanisms is crucial for promoting a holistic well-being. This study explores these coping strategies and their influence on the mental well-being of the Zulu and Maasai communities in the urban settings of Johannesburg, South Africa, and Nairobi, Kenya. As varied communities with rich cultural histories, Maasai and Zulu people provide a unique scope to examine the nuanced relationship.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Knowledge of indigenous cultural systems of health coping habits and strategies is essential in the development of culturally relevant interventions for mental health care improvement amongst populations. When people are exposed to a stressor, they often employ varying ways of dealing with the stressor and these are termed coping mechanisms, which may become consistent in varying settings, situations and time. They can be internal or learnt through social structures of families and culture, (Algorani, & Gupta, 2023). In Africa, indigenous cultural systems are traditionally respected, followed and sought out in the quest for health improvements. Mental health is a fundamental element of wellbeing. Understanding and creating mental health care is often challenging in various cultural settings in Africa. Existing research has primarily focused on Western perspectives and modalities of treatment which has limited inclusion of culturally specific strategies that contribute to the coping with mental wellbeing of the Zulu and Maasai people.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Mental health is an important element of our lives. However, there is still a gap in understanding the integration of culturally relevant coping strategies within the context of African communities. This study aims to explore these coping strategies and provide important insights for continued integration of mental health strategies that resonate with the unique needs and cultural frameworks in an African context

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this study were to examine the coping mechanisms utilized by the Zulu and Maasai communities and assess their influence on mental well-being. Specifically, the study aimed to identify the predominant coping methods employed within each cultural group, to analyze how these coping strategies affect individual mental well-being, and to compare the effectiveness of these strategies across the two communities. By achieving these objectives, the study sought to generate culturally informed insights that can inform contextually appropriate mental health interventions in African urban contexts.

1.5 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The study was guided by the hypothesis that coping mechanisms had an effect on the mental well-being of Zulu and Maasai individuals (H_1), while the null hypothesis (H_0) stated that coping mechanisms did not affect mental well-being. Several assumptions underpinned the research, including that participants responded honestly to the research instruments and willingly shared their true experiences related to coping

strategies and mental well-being. These assumptions were critical to ensuring the validity and reliability of the findings. The study was justified by its potential to generate culturally sensitive insights that could inform mental health interventions within African communities, particularly by integrating indigenous coping mechanisms into formal support strategies. However, the study faced limitations, such as the possibility of social desirability bias, with participants potentially selecting favorable responses to protect cultural identity. To address this, the researcher assured participants of confidentiality and anonymity to encourage more candid and accurate disclosures.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review explores the conceptual, theoretical, and empirical facets of this study. The researcher examines the foundational concepts of this study. It seeks to form an understanding of the existing knowledge and research variables and inform this study.

2.1 Theoretical framework

This study has its framework embedded in the Transactional model of Stress and Coping (TSC) by Lazarus and Folkman, (1984). Effective coping to any stressful situation is dependent on the individual's cognitive appraisal of the stressful event and the subsequent behavioural coping mechanism applied, (Schaufeli, 2015). The model serves as a transactional guideline in the examination of the dynamics of coping mechanisms and how they interact in Maasai and Zulu cultures. According to Lazarus and Folkman they are two aspects to managing a stressor; that is firstly: *problem-based coping* which involves the practical steps you take to manage a problem and secondly the *emotion-based coping*, that is how one manages emotions in the face of a stressful situation. How one responds to the challenging situation has a higher impact on the stress level than the event itself. According to Algorani et al (2023), studies that employ a problem focused approach proved to be most suitable and beneficial for participants.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The study draws from the TSC model, by Lazarus and Folkman (1984). This model provides a conceptual understanding of the effect of coping mechanisms on the mental wellbeing of the current; two cultures of study. The model provides a cognitive and behavioural process individuals in the Maasai and Zulu cultures engage in a response to external and internal stressor stimuli. The *primary appraisal* (impact of the stressor) presents the perceived stressors and activates the assessment of the meaning attached to the stressor related to mental wellbeing by the individual, (Schaufeli, 2015). The *secondary appraisal* (resource for managing the stressor) then presents the evaluation and selection of coping resources and strategies within the cultural context, values, perceptions, norms, and practices. The *coping mechanisms* (problem-based or emotional based coping) present the strategies employed by the individuals in the Zulu and Maasai communities, such as culturally specific methodologies that address the stressor stimuli whether internal or external from both a community and personal element. Lastly, analysis the impact of coping strategies on mental wellbeing in the two cultural contexts with the consideration of both the adaptive and maladaptive strategies. TSC as a conceptual framework provides the relationship between the coping mechanisms and mental wellbeing in the unique cultural scope of this study. Below is an illustration of conceptual framework for this study.

2.2.1 Coping mechanisms

Coping mechanisms are the varying ways employed by individuals to dealing with various stressor stimuli (internally or externally), these could be cognitive or behavioural, which may become consistent in varying settings, situations and time, (Algorani et al, 2023). Coping mechanisms can be *problem-based* that is the practical steps taken to manage the stressor or *emotion-based* that is the management of emotions and concepts the self, according to Schaufeli, (2015). *Support structures* is defined as system that aids, encouragement and motivation to persons to help them cope in various situations or achieve a particular goal, (Hood, 2020, Frouhari, Hosseini Teshnizi, Ehrampoush, 2019).

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for coping mechanisms effects of mental wellbeing: Researcher: 2023

According to Hood, (2020) having a strong support system has many positive benefits such as high levels of wellbeing, good quality of life, coping skills and a healthier life. Studies have shown that having a support system reduces depression and anxiety symptoms, (Hood, 2020). *Cultural practices* decisions and activities performed towards the upkeep of one's life based on their cultural contexts. Sinescu and Răban-Motounu, (2019) stated that studies have found more people engaging in cultural and religious practices to manage stressors effectively.

Religious Practices are behaviours motivated by religious beliefs such as prayer, church attendances and the use of symbols. Crocq, (2015) states that many studies have explored the relationships between religion and mental health and found them to reduce the levels of anxiety. Research illustrates that many people's, religious beliefs and practices may have positive impact on mental health outcomes. Religion has been shown to provide beliefs of comfort, improved coping and social functioning as well as hope and social support.

Recreational activities are defined as activities of leisure often done for enjoyment amusement or pleasure and an essential element of human biology and psychology (meditation, reading, dancing, walking). Recreational activities help with refreshing the mind and body and helps with relaxation, which is an essential part of positive coping, (Khasnabis, Heinicke Motsch, Achu, et al, 2010). *Professional mental help* is defined as the assistance provided for mental health by trained and qualified mental health service providers such as psychologists, to address, diagnose and provide interventions for mental health and wellbeing,

(Ogueji, & Okoloba, 2022). Seeking mental health assistance is necessary for persons who face mental health issues to develop coping strategies and understanding and gain an overall improvement of mental health problems.

2.2.2 *Mental Wellbeing*

Emotional Stability is the ability of a person to maintain a balanced and resilient emotional state in the face significant stressors and general challenges. People with a good emotional intelligence and stability are often more skilled at cope with their emotions and demonstrate consistency in mood, (Chaturvedi, & Chander, 2010). *Connectedness* refers to a sense of belonging and attachment as well as integration that one feels in a relationship with others and society. It is a sense of belonging in social, family, religious or cultural bonds that fosters resilience and wellbeing, (O'Rourke, & Sidani, 2017).

2.3 Empirical Evidence

There is limited research on mental health coping that is culturally specific. Much work still needs to be done. A study was conducted in Kwa-Zulu Natal by Thwala, Hermann, & Edwards, et al (2020) with 18 participants (9 males and females) mean age of 46,83 (15-80 years range). The study focused on the coping mechanisms of Zulu people during COVID-19 where the variables included emotional experiences. Participants who were affluent in education demonstrated resilient strength and adaptive coping. Coping mechanisms included harmonious interpersonal, social and spiritual relationships as well as ancestral consciousness, religious practices, and community relationships and indigenous knowledge of medicines. Another study by Forouhari, et al (2019) highlighted a Swiss study were patients diagnosed with schizophrenia benefited greatly through the practice of religious activities as they displayed fewer negative symptoms and an improved social functioning and quality of life 3 years after. According to Daniel, Njau & Mtuya et al, (2018), the Maasai have pluralistic help-seeking behaviour for mental health disorders where they apply multiple factors to their treatment options. In their study on the perceptions and mental health seeking behaviour on 41 participants (20 male and 21 female) across 7 districts, the study found that, Maasai community practice religion, traditional and professional health care to cope.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Methodology:

This study employs a comparative quantitative research design to investigate coping mechanisms and their impact on the mental well-being of Zulu and Maasai communities in Johannesburg, South Africa, and Nairobi, Kenya. The approach involved a structured questionnaire administered to 20 adults from each community, selected using the stratified random sampling method. The research employed statistical analyses, to compare coping mechanisms and their influence on mental well-being.

3.2 Participant Selection:

The sampling method applied in this study is stratified random sampling amongst Zulu and Maasai (10 samples each). The selection criteria: age, gender, ethnicity, and education levels.

3.3 Research Instrument and Collection:

The instruments developed by the researchers was applied in this study; a structured questionnaire, Cul-

tural Well-being Inventory (CWI), with 4 domains of cultural background (D1), coping mechanisms, (D2), mental wellbeing (D3) and evaluative domain (D4). D1-D3 were structured questions on a Likert Scale ranging from 1-5 with 1 being (never) and 5 being (always) and D4 was an open-ended question to allow evaluative perceptions on the study subject. The questionnaire was administered as an online survey.

3.4 Variables:

The independent variables of the study were, coping mechanisms, while dependent variables were mental well-being and control variables, demographic factors, cultural background.

3.5 Ethical Considerations:

Informed consent, confidentiality and cultural sensitivity are prioritized and outlined for all participants before the completion of the questionnaire.

3.6 Data Analysis:

A quantitative data analysis was done using statistical inferences of Pearson correlation to measure the strength and the direction of the linear relationship between coping mechanism and mental well-being (positive or negative). The standard deviation was used to quantify the consistency and variability of the measurements in data sets between the dependent and independent variables in the two communities. A cross-cultural analysis to evaluate effectiveness of coping mechanisms was employed in domain 4 of the questionnaire.

3.7 Data Validity and Reliability:

Data validity and reliability was insured through the implementation of standardised online data collection protocols to maintain consistency and accuracy across all elements in the study.

3.8 Results Interpretation:

A comparative analysis of coping mechanisms, their influence on mental well-being, and identification of cultural variations were employed in this study. A discussion will be facilitated on the implications for mental health interventions and strategies as cultural considerations.

3.9 Limitations:

The consideration of the specificity of the Zulu and Maasai cultures for generalizability and recognising the sample size and diversity within the two communities.

4. FINDINGS

Table 1: Demographic data.

	DEMOGRAPHICS	ZULU PARTICIPANTS N=10	MAASAI PARTICI- PANTS N=10
AGE	30 -39	5	4
	40-49	5	6
GENDER	Male	5	5
	Female	5	5
EDUCA- TIONAL LEV- ELS	None	0	0
	Primary education	1	2
	Secondary school	4	2
	College/university	5	6

The Zulu cross-cultural examination begins by outlining the age distribution among the 10 participants, outlining a balanced division in the two groups: 30-39 and 40-49, each constituting 50% of the population study sample. This representation across age reflected an inclusive sampling. Gender demographics presented a balance of five males (N=5) and five females (N=5), each comprising 50% of the study sample. The integration of age and gender was crucial in the examination of insights and avoiding overgeneralizations. Additionally, the educational level distribution provides valuable context, with no participants reporting no formal education. One (1) participant completed primary education (10%), four (4), secondary school education (40%), and the majority, constituting five (5) individuals (50%), completed tertiary education.

These demographic insights collectively contribute to the analysis, acknowledging the significance of age, gender, and education in shaping individual experiences in the examination of the objective of this study. The Maasai demographic breakdown was based on a sample size of 10 participants illuminating age distribution, with four (4) individuals (40%) falling within the 30-39 age range and the remaining six (60%) belonging to the 40-49 age range. The gender distribution, however, stood out for its balance, with five (N=5) males and five (N=5) females included to capture the range of perspectives, each constituting 50% of the study sample. This gender equilibrium helped unveil gender-specific traditions and roles within the Maasai community. The educational level distribution for both populations adds another layer to the analysis, indicating a relatively well-educated sample, with none reporting no formal education, two (N=2) completing primary education (20%), two (N=2) attaining secondary school education (20%), and the majority, constituting six (N=6) participants (60%), having pursued higher education at the university level. Despite these insights, the study emphasizes caution in generalizing findings to the broader Maasai population, given the constraints of the small sample size at the time of study.

4.1 Zulu Participant Scores

Zulu scores: N=10			1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree										
Domain	No	Items	Participants scores										
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
D1(Cultural background)	1	How strongly do you identify with your cultural heritage?	4	4	4	2	5	5	3	3	2	4	
	2	Seeking support from family and community during challenging times.	4	3	3	4	3	2	3	3	3	3	
D2 (Coping Mechanism)	3	Engaging in traditional rituals or practices for emotional support.	3	3	5	1	3	5	3	2	2	3	
	4	Seeking professional help such as counselling, therapy when facing difficulties.	3	5	2	5	1	1	2	3	2	3	
	5	Engaging in physical activities or exercise as a means of coping.	5	5	3	5	1	1	1	1	2	3	
	6	Expressing emotions through creative outlets (art, music, dance).	2	5	3	5	2	1	2	5	2	5	
D3 (Mental Well-being)	7	Using religious or spiritual practices for emotional support.	4	3	4	3	5	5	2	3	1	4	
	8	I feel emotionally balanced and stable in my daily life.	3	4	3	4	3	2	3	4	3	4	
	9	I feel connected and supported within my community	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
	10	I am able to effectively manage stress and challenges.	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	4	2	4
	11	I experience a sense of purpose and fulfilment in my life.	4	4	4	4	3	2	3	4	2	4	
	12	I feel in control of my emotions and reactions.	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4
	13	I feel comfortable discussing mental health within my community.	4	3	2	2	3	1	1	2	1	1	
TOTAL SCORE:			4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	2	4	
			6	9	4	5	8	4	2	0	8	5	

4.2 Zulu Participants: Variability and Consistency

Table: Zulu Participants Responses per domain

Do main	Partici- pants	μ = Mean	σ = Standard Devia- tion
D1	1	4	1.41
D1	2	4	1.41
D1	3	4	1.17
D1	4	2	1.07
D1	5	5	2.09
D1	6	5	1.17
D1	7	3	1.22
D1	8	3	1.41
D1	9	2	1.22
D1	10	4	1.41
D2	1	3.3	0.55
D2	2	3.3	0.55
D2	3	3.1	1.17
D2	4	3.2	1.07
D2	5	3.7	2.09
D2	6	3.2	1.17
D2	7	3.4	1.22
D2	8	3	1.41
D2	9	2.4	1.22
D2	10	3	1.41
D3	1	3	0.82
D3	2	3	0.82
D3	3	3	0.82
D3	4	3	0.82
D3	5	3	0.82
D3	6	3	0.82
D3	7	3.4	0.82
D3	8	3	0.82
D3	9	3	0.82
D3	10	3	0.82

D1: Cultural Background: The participants showed varying levels of agreement their responses. Participant 5 had the highest ($\sigma = 2.09$), indicating the highest adaptability to cultural background in responses, while Participant 4 had the lowest ($\sigma = 1.07$), suggesting more consistent answers. The participants on average stated a moderate level with a mean score of (3.5) and a variability in strength of cultural identification, ($\sigma = 1.04$)

D2: Coping Mechanism: In this domain participant 5 had the highest ($\sigma = 2.09$), indicating diverse response in relation to coping mechanisms, while participant 2 had the lowest ($\sigma = 0.55$), suggesting more uniformity in perceptions. In scores the items in religious or spiritual practices for emotional support, had the highest mean score of (3.4), engaging in traditional rituals or practices for emotional support, (3.3), seeking support from family and community, (3.2), physical activities, (3.0) and expressing emotions through creative outlets, (3.0). professional help such as counselling, the lowest (2.7). Participants has a moderate to high preference of various coping mechanisms.

D3: Mental well-being: In D3, participants 5 and 7 both had the highest ($\sigma = 0.82$), showing more varied responses. Participants 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, and 10 all had the lowest standard deviation ($\sigma = 0.82$), reflecting relatively consistent responses to mental well-being perceptions. Experience a sense of purpose and fulfilment in life had the highest score of (3,8), while feeling in control of my emotions and reactions, (3,6), ability to effectively manage stress and challenges, (3,5), connectedness and support within my community, (3,0). the lowest score was the comfort to discuss mental health within my community. (2,8). Participants expressed a moderate preference in mental wellbeing overall.

Table: Overall Zulu Participants Responses per domain

Domain	σ - Standard Devia- tion
D1 (Cultural Back- ground)	1.04
D2 (Coping Mecha- nism)	0.81
D3 (Mental Well- being)	0.69

The findings of the study based on the Zulu community results show a notable pattern of participants responses across different domains. Cultural Background (D1) domain shows that; there was a moderate level of dispersion ($\sigma = 1.04$), indicating diversity in how strongly individuals identify with their cultural practices. Coping Mechanisms (D2) domain presented a slightly lower dispersion ($\sigma = 0.81$), suggesting a more consistent response in seeking support and applying various coping mechanisms. Mental well-being (D3) domain demonstrated the lowest dispersion ($\sigma = 0.69$), showing a moderately consistent perception of emotional balance, community support as well as stress management among participants in the study. The study findings suggested a moderate level of engagement in cultural practices for mental health coping among Zulu participants, though individual differences exist reflecting the cultural variability that is expected within any group.

4.3 Zulu Participants: Evaluative Domain:

D4 (Evaluative Q)	14	In your own words, could you describe a specific coping mechanism or cultural practice that you find particularly impactful in managing stress or challenges
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The Evaluative domain responses from Zulu participants, shed some light on the dynamics of cultural identity, mental health openness, and coping mechanisms. (30%) of the participants had a reserved expression and limited engagement with cultural and traditional practices on the open-ended questions. This may be attributed to the prevalent stigma within the Zulu community. The emerging themes showed that participants offered a contrasting viewpoint, highlighting the transformative influence of cultural gatherings as a coping mechanism, where stories are shared, and mutual support is fostered. (N=3) participants expressed that they found solace and a profound sense of belonging and highlighted the shared strength derived from cultural values of unity and the role of community and cultural identity in building resilience during challenging times. This perspective highlights the potential for communal practices not only as coping mechanisms but as essential components of cultural identity and well-being. (N=2) participant confirmed their coping mechanism of cultural meditation. (N=1) participant stated engagement in traditional medicines to heal the body and mind. (N=2) participants were reserved in stating actual experiences but generally expressed cultural practices are helpful in finding strength. (80%) of this group generally agreed and recognized the importance of coping mechanisms and (60%) stated they practice these activities, showing a moderate level of in cultural activities as coping mechanisms for mental wellbeing.

4.4 Correlation Analysis among Zulu Participants

In the Zulu community there appears to be a moderate to significant negative connection ($r = -0.71090439$) between mental well-being (D3) and coping techniques (D2). The negative sign indicates that mental health tends to decline with an increase in coping mechanisms, or vice versa. According to the standard 0.05 significance threshold, the observed correlation is not statistically significant, as indicated by the t-statistic of -2.02165746 with degrees of freedom (DF) of 4. Nonetheless, given the p-value of 0.0945 is near the significance level, and may be classified as moderately significant.

Table: Zulu Participants correlation analysis:

X (D2) COPING MECHANISMS	X (D3) MENTAL WELLBEING			
3,1				3,3
3				3,1
2,7				3,3
2,7				3,4
3,2				3,3
3,4				2
Coefficient (r):	N:	T statistic	Degrees of freedom	P Value:
-0,71090439	6	-2,02166	4	0.0945

4.5 Maasai Participant scores

Maasai Response scores:			1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree									
Domain	N	items	Participant responses									
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
D1(Cultural background)	1	How strongly do you identify with your cultural heritage?	4	5	5	2	5	5	4	4	4	4
D2(Coping Mechanism)	2	Seeking support from family and community during challenging times.	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	3
	3	Engaging in traditional rituals or practices for emotional support.	5	4	4	2	3	4	3	4	4	3
	4	Seeking professional help such as counselling, therapy when facing difficulties.	3	2	3	2	1	3	4	3	2	3
	5	Engaging in physical activities or exercise as a means of coping.	4	2	5	1	3	4	1	3	2	3
	6	Expressing emotions through creative outlets (art, music, dance).	2	3	2	3	3	2	3	4	3	3
	7	Using religious or spiritual practices for emotional support.	4	5	5	2	5	5	2	3	1	4
	D3 (Mental Well-being)	8	I feel emotionally balanced and stable in my daily life.	3	4	3	4	4	4	3	3	3
9		I feel connected and supported within my community	4	3	4	3	4	3	4	5	3	5
10		I am able to effectively manage stress and challenges.	3	4	4	3	2	3	3	3	2	3
11		I experience a sense of purpose and fulfilment in my life.	5	5	3	2	3	3	3	5	3	4
12		I feel in control of my emotions and reactions.	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	4	4	3
13	I feel comfortable discussing mental health within my community?	4	4	3	1	2	2	1	3	3	2	
TOTAL SCORE			49	47	48	31	31	45	48	38	48	33

4.6 Maasai Variability and Consistency

Table: Maasai Participants Responses per domain Variability and Consistency

Domain	Participant	Mean	σ =Standard Deviation
D1	1	4.4	1.03
D1	2	4.6	0.89
D1	3	4.6	0.89
D1	4	2.9	1.58
D1	5	4.6	0.89
D1	6	4.6	0.89
D1	7	4.3	0.92
D1	8	4.4	0.92
D1	9	4.4	0.92
D1	10	4.4	0.92
D2	1	3.6	0.55
D2	2	3.6	0.55
D2	3	3.4	0.55
D2	4	2.7	0.89
D2	5	2.7	1.34
D2	6	2.9	0.89
D2	7	3.6	0.55
D2	8	3.6	0.55
D2	9	3.6	0.55
D2	10	3.4	0.55
D3	1	3.2	0.75
D3	2	3.6	0.55
D3	3	3.8	0.75
D3	4	3.1	0.89
D3	5	3.9	0.92
D3	6	3.9	0.55
D3	7	3.7	0.75
D3	8	3.9	0.55
D3	9	3.4	0.75
D3	10	3.7	0.75

D1: Cultural Background

Participants in D1, on Cultural Background, generally showed a high mean score (4.3), indicating a strong identification with their cultural heritage. The values, ranging from ($\sigma=0.89$) to ($\sigma=1.58$), suggests some flexibility in responses. Participant 4 showed a lower mean and higher standard deviation, indicating a greater diversity in their responses, possibly reflecting a less uniform connection to cultural heritage.

D2: Coping Mechanism

Coping Mechanism- D1, participants reported moderate mean scores, ranging from 2.7 to 3.6. The ($\sigma=0.55$), suggested relatively consistent responses in this domain. Participant 5 exhibited a higher standard deviation of ($\sigma=1.34$), indicated greater variability in coping mechanism. Participant responses showed seeking support from religious or spiritual practices for emotional support had the highest mean of (3.9) while family and community, mean of (3.5) and traditional practice for emotional support (3.3), and expressing through emotional support (3.0) received moderate scores as the preference. Seeking professional help had a low score of (2.9)

This may suggest diverse coping strategies in the group.

Domain 3: Mental Well-being

In D3, Mental Well-being, participants reported mean scores ranging from mean, (3.1) to (3.9). The values, ranging from ($\sigma=0.55$ to ($\sigma=0.92$), suggested a moderate level of variability in responses of feeling emotionally balanced and stable in their daily lives. The relatively low standard deviation ($\sigma = 0.75$) suggests a consistent perception of emotional balance among respondents. Participants generally reported slight variations. Notably, participant 5 reported a higher mean and standard deviation, suggesting a broader range of experiences related to mental well-being.

Table: Overall Maasai Participants Responses per domain

Domain	σ =Standard Deviation
D1 (Cultural Background)	1.070
D2 (Coping Mechanism)	0.897
D3 (Mental Well-being)	1.059

Maasai participants illustrated consistent responses across all domains of the study. The were ($\sigma=1.070$) for cultural background (D1), ($\sigma=0.897$) for Coping Mechanism (D2), and ($\sigma=1.059$) for Mental Well-being (D3). Values from findings suggest a moderate level of variability in cultural practices, coping mechanisms, and perceptions of well-being within the group. Overall, the findings indicate a consistent yet diverse range of experiences among the Maasai participants.

4.7 Maasai Evaluative Domain

D4 (Evaluative Q)	14	In your own words, could you describe a specific coping mechanism or cultural practice that you find particularly impactful in managing stress or challenges
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In the Maasai group some response from (30%) of the Maasai participants stated emphasized the significant coping mechanism of gathering around the evening fire to share their problems. This cultural practice was stated as providing both physical and emotional warmth, fostering a supportive environment through shared stories, wisdom, and challenges. The participants highlight the transformative nature of this tradition, symbolically represented by the crackling flames carrying away burdens. The cultural practice was further stated as contributing to a sense of belonging and guidance, showcasing the significant role of this practice in stress management. In contrast, the second response, (20%) of participants revealed challenges in society’s perception of mental health. Mental illness was associated with, witchcraft, curses, and divine punishment, reflecting significant traditional beliefs. The participants expressed challenges with connecting with society, indicating a potential barrier to open dialogue on mental health problems. for more inclusive conversations within the community. Both responses show the intricate relationship between cultural practices and mental well-being in the Maasai community. The first illustrates positive cultural support and resilience, the second brings insight into challenges rooted in cultural beliefs that may affect mental health support dialogues.

4.8 Maasai Participants: Correlation Analysis amongst Maasai participants

X (D2) COPING MECHANISMS	X (D3) MENTAL WELLBEING
3,4	3,4
3,6	3,8
2,6	3
2,8	3,6
2,8	3,5
3,6	2,5

Coefficient (r):	N:	T statistic	Degrees of freedom	P Value:
-0,112640889	6	-0,22672	4	0.824

4.9 Variability and Consistency: Maasai and Zulu Comparisons

Tabel: Variability and consistency for Zulu and Maasai participants across different domains:

Domain	Zulu Participants	Maasai Participants
D1 (Cultural Background)	$\sigma = 1.04$	$\sigma = 1.070$
D2 (Coping Mechanism)	$\sigma = 0.81$	$\sigma = 0.897$
D3 (Mental Well-being)	$\sigma = 0.69$	$\sigma = 1.059$

In comparative analysis on the Zulu and Maasai community responses, both groups demonstrated a diverse distinct pattern. The Zulu participants, in the cultural background (D1) domain, exhibited a moderate level of variability ($\sigma = 1.04$), demonstrating diversity in coping mechanisms. In the coping mechanisms (D2) domain, the Zulu group exhibited slightly more consistency ($\sigma = 0.81$), suggesting a consistency in the responses to seeking support and coping strategies. For mental well-being (D3), the Zulu participants displayed the lowest dispersion ($\sigma = 0.69$), indicating a relatively consistent perception of emotional balance and stress management. Maasai participants demonstrated consistent responses across all domains;

($\sigma=1.070$) and for cultural background (D1), ($\sigma=0.897$) for coping mechanism (D2), and ($\sigma=1.059$) for mental well-being (D3). These differences highlight the unique cultural dynamics within each community, emphasizing the importance of considering specific cultural contexts when interpreting mental health-related responses. Zulu participants in coping mechanism (D2) had a standard deviation (σ) of 0.81, indicating a relatively consistent response to coping strategies. Maasai participants in coping mechanism exhibited a higher standard deviation ($\sigma=1.34$), suggesting greater variability in coping methods.

4.10 Maasai and Zulu Participants: Correlation Analysis

Participants:	Coefficient (r):	N:	T statistic	Degrees of freedom	P Value:
Maasai:	-0,112640889	6	-	4	0.824
Zulu:	-0,71090439	6	-	4	0.0945
			2,02166		

Numerous factors may affect variations in the correlation's strength and significance between the two populations. These differences could be attributed to individual beliefs of mental health and coping, cultural differences, and society standards. Furthermore, the lack of statistical significance in the p-values suggests that the correlations identified in both populations may be influenced by casual events rather than association between mental health and coping strategies. To draw more reliable conclusions, it is imperative that additional studies and a deeper comprehension of cultural nuances be explored. The observed trends may have been shaped by cultural factors, varying coping techniques and views, which emphasizes the significance of taking cultural context into account in mental health research.

5. DISCUSSION AND RESEARCH CONCLUSION

The study aimed at examining coping mechanisms and their influence on mental well-being among Zulu and Maasai communities in Johannesburg, South Africa and Nairobi Kenya. This chapter presents the discussion based on the study objectives and research conclusion.

5.1 Overall Discussion

The findings of the study underscore the unique cultural dynamics influencing mental health perceptions in each community. The first objective of the study was to identify coping methods in the Zulu and Maasai communities. The findings of the study presented a diverse coping method for the Zulu participants, including engaging in cultural practices and seeking support. The Maasai highlighted the significance of gathering around the evening fire and revealed challenges associated with mental health perceptions. The second objective of the study was to analyze the influence of coping strategies on mental well-being in each community. The study indicated that coping strategies have a notable impact on mental well-being within each of the two community. In the Zulu group, the effectiveness of coping strategies is reflected in the moderate consistency of responses in cultural practices, coping mechanisms, and perceptions of mental well-being. Similarly, within the Maasai participants the group exhibited consistent responses across all domains, emphasizing the influence of coping strategies on their mental well-being. The third objective was to compare the effectiveness of coping strategies on mental well-being between the Zulu and Maasai. The comparison reveals distinct patterns between the two communities. The Zulu group demonstrated a moderate level of variability in their responses, suggesting a varied set of individual experiences within their cultural context. On the other hand,

the Maasai participants exhibited more consistent responses, highlighting the effectiveness of coping strategies within their cultural framework.

5.2 Research Hypothesis:

The hypothesis of this study was that coping mechanisms influence mental well-being of Zulu and Maasai individuals. The null hypothesis was that coping mechanisms do not affect the mental well-being of Zulu and Maasai individuals.

5.3 Analysis of Relationships between Variables

On the basis of the statistical analysis, the correlation coefficients (r) for both the Maasai ($r = -0.1126$) and Zulu ($r = -0.7109$) communities were assessed. The Maasai, correlation was negative but not a statistically significant (T statistic = -0.2267 , $p = 0.824$), showing a weak association between coping mechanisms and mental well-being. The Zulu, correlation was negative and approached significance (T statistic = -2.0217 , $p = 0.0945$), suggesting a potential connection between coping mechanisms and the mental well-being, however not reaching the conventional levels of significance. Therefore, based on the statistical evidence, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, as the experimental correlations do not stipulate a strong support for the hypothesis that; coping mechanisms have a significant effect on the mental well-being of both Zulu and Maasai participants. In conclusion, this study explored coping mechanisms and their impact on mental well-being within the Zulu and Maasai communities in Johannesburg, South Africa, and Nairobi, Kenya. The findings of the study showed a distinct and cultural dynamics coping mechanisms shaping mental wellbeing in each community. The findings of this study contribute valuable insights into the cultural dynamics of coping mechanisms and their impact on mental well-being within the Zulu and Maasai communities. Findings suggest the need for further exploration with a larger sample size to potentially uncover a more conclusive relationship.

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Annexture A – Research Instrument: Cultural Well-being Inventory (CWI)

Research Questionnaire Overview

A structured questionnaire Cultural Well-being Inventory (CWI), focusing on coping mechanisms and mental well-being among the Zulu and Maasai communities, utilising 14 questions on a Likert scale where 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree from section A to E with E being an evaluative question where you are required to briefly explain in writing the reason behind your rating.

Instructions for participants:

- i. **Confidentiality:** Your responses are totally anonymous. Please answer the questions honestly and to the best of your ability. Your participation is voluntary.
- ii. **Honest Responses:** Your honest opinions and responses to experiences are important to the success of this study. There are no right or wrong answers as we are interested in your personal perspectives.
- iii. **Guidance for completing the questionnaire:**
 - Please read each question carefully and choose the response that best suits or represents your thoughts or actions.
 - Use the Likert scale (1 to 5) and instructions provided on each question to show your agreement or rate of engagement with the given statement,
 - Complete the questionnaire in one sitting.
 - The questionnaire will take approximately 5-8 minutes to complete.
 - If you have any questions about this research, please contact the researcher on the details provided above.
 - Once you have answered all the questions, please return the questionnaire as instructed.

Scoring Procedure:

The scoring for this questionnaire involves assigning numerical values to participants' responses based on the Likert scale. The Likert scale typically ranges from 1 to 5, representing levels of agreement, frequency, or perception. Each response (1 to 5) from question 1-13 will be tallied for every item. Higher scores indicate a greater frequency or agreement with the statement.

- B. Cultural Background Section (Question 1)
- C. Coping Mechanisms Section (Questions 2-7)
- D. Mental Well-being Section (Questions 8-13)

Section E is an evaluative question. Responses from participants will be analysed qualitatively to support the findings of the study. E. Evaluative Question [open-ended] (Questions 14)

Cultural Well-being Inventory (CWI)

A. Demographic Information:							
Age:	Write your age:						
Gender	Male		Female		Other:		Prefer not to say
Ethnicity:	Zulu		Maasai				
Educational Level:	No formal Education		Secondary School				
	Primary Education		College/University				

Please rate the responses to the following statements using the Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree from section B to E with E being an evaluative question where you are required to briefly explain in writing your response for question 14.

No.	ITEMS	1 Never	2 Rarely	3 Sometimes	4 Often	5 Always
B. Cultural Background:						
1.	How strongly do you identify with your cultural heritage?					
C. Coping Mechanisms:						
2	Seeking support from family and community during challenging times.					
3	Engaging in traditional rituals or practices for emotional support.					
4	Seeking professional help such as counselling, therapy when facing difficulties.					
5	Engaging in physical activities or exercise as a means of coping.					
6	Expressing emotions through creative outlets (art, music, dance).					
7	Using religious or spiritual practices for emotional support.					
D. Mental Well-being						
8	I feel emotionally balanced and stable in my daily life.					
9	I feel connected and supported within my community					
10	I am able to effectively manage stress and challenges.					
11	I experience a sense of purpose and fulfilment in my life.					
12	I feel in control of my emotions and reactions.					
13	I feel comfortable discussing mental health within my community?					
E. Evaluative Question [open-ended]						
14	In your own words, could you describe a specific coping mechanism or cultural practice that you find particularly impactful in managing stress or challenges					
	<i>(Briefly explain in writing your response for question 14 below).</i>					